

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D2.2 *PARCopedia* scoping document WP 2

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¹ PU = Public

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Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/institution	Short description of changes
1	2022-12-20	BfR	First draft for discussion within Task 2.2
2	2023-01-10	BfR	Second draft integrating comments and revisions from Task 2.2 partners
3	2023-02-13	BfR	Third draft integrating comments from MB and other PARC WPs, and inclusive of the annex on technical specifications
4	2023-02-20	BfR	Fourth draft, integrating comments from WP3, WP7 and T2.2.
5	2023-02-28	BfR	Fifth draft, for review by the WP 2 co-leads
6	2023-03-15	BfR	Final draft to be sent to Coordination Team
7	2023-04-21	BfR	Final version incorporating the comments from the reviewers, to be submitted to the European Commission

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Abstract

The European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) aims to develop as well as promote innovation in Chemical Risk Assessment (CRA), with particular focus on New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) and Next-Generation Risk assessment (NGRA), to protect human health and the environment with state-of-the-art science. PARC will develop scientifically robust assessment methods and tools, with a strong attention to significantly reduce the use of laboratory animals for testing of chemical substances. The Partnership provides a unique and unprecedented opportunity to bring together scientists, regulators, national and European agencies as well as policy makers, thus promoting the constructive exchange of points of view, and the uptake of innovation into regulatory practice.

To this end, *PARCopedia*, the PARC knowledge management platform, will provide an online space for users to consult and share knowledge relevant to chemical risk assessment, and a tool to facilitate interdisciplinary exchange within the diverse chemical risk assessment community. *PARCopedia* will offer PARC Work Packages and other related EU research projects a platform for presenting their work and the progress made therein. It will also provide a wiki-type knowledge base covering all aspects of chemical risk assessment, and a community space to connect peers and colleagues from different disciplines, sectors and areas of work. A powerful search engine will allow to efficiently browse relevant information on different chemicals/chemical groups, risk assessment methodologies (including exposure and toxicity), and relevant legislations.

PARCopedia will be open to users from both in and outside of PARC after registration, including researchers, risk assessors, risk managers and policy makers that have a general understanding of the chemical risk assessment processes, but who may have different ideas or points of view based on their different sectors, areas of work, and expertise.

In this way, *PARCopedia* will become one of the central tools for bringing the idea of a partnership to life, distinguishing PARC from previous EU framework projects. It will enable solutions that have been discussed by a significant part of the chemical risk assessment community and are therefore well-prepared for timely regulatory uptake.

With this document we provide the starting point for the implementation and rollout of a first version of the *PARCopedia* platform (due by PARC M18) as well as its further development in the coming years.

Key Words

PARCopedia; knowledge management; chemical risk assessment; community platform; PARC; partnership; knowledge sharing.

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Executive summary

This document provides the conceptual basis for the technical implementation and rollout of *PARCopedia*, the knowledge management platform of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC).

PARC aims at innovating chemical risk assessment (CRA) in line with the European Commission’s “Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability”. It brings together a huge network of European researchers, risk assessors and policy makers, covering and connecting a large part of the European as well as a significant fraction of the global CRA community.

PARCopedia intends to become the central online meeting place for PARC as well as the larger CRA community. It will facilitate knowledge sharing and discussion on CRA innovation, thereby fostering a broad and deep understanding of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) and their role in CRA. This will then be a key step for achieving broad acceptance of the transition from the current *in vivo* testing paradigm towards Next-Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) in European chemicals legislation in the future.

PARCopedia will be composed of 1) a comprehensive knowledge base covering the majority CRA aspects, 2) a powerful search engine for CRA-related knowledge on substances, methods, and processes, and 3) a lively community space with expert profiles, discussion fora and other tools to share knowledge on innovative CRA approaches as well as related activities and projects.

Content featured in *PARCopedia* will include knowledge on, or relevant for, 1) the risk assessment of chemicals or chemical groups, 2) experimental and non-experimental methods or approaches that can be used to provide data for the assessment of chemicals, risk or exposure assessment methodologies or approaches, 3) legislation on chemicals and 4) any technical result produced within PARC. The community space within *PARCopedia* will consist of profiles summarising the users’ work and expertise, blogs to share relevant work and ideas and discussion fora to interact with other users on chemical risk assessment topics.

Connections with other PARC platforms, tools and different PARC working packages will be ensured, with the PARC website remaining the site for official PARC communications. The

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content in *PARCopedia* will be organised based on the multiple dimensions of chemical risk assessment.

While the overall management and governance of *PARCopedia* will be in the hand of PARC Task 2.2 (PARC's task responsible for *PARCopedia*), PARC chemical and methodology leaders will play an important role for providing content and quality controls. Users will bear full individual responsibility and accountability for the content they provide in their profiles, blogs or comments made to other content in *PARCopedia*, but author rights to create and change content within the wiki or WP sections will only be provided to selected users. All authors will be responsible for complying with the authorship guidelines and policy of *PARCopedia*.

PARCopedia will only contain non-confidential information. Registration to the *PARCopedia* platform will be open to everyone subject to a registration process, where the full real name and other information will be required. To engage in the community space, users will need to accept the codes of conduct and guidelines of *PARCopedia* upon registration. Defamatory, abusive, threatening, offensive or illegal material will be strictly prohibited. Discriminatory, hostile or intimidating messages or language will not be tolerated.

A beta version of *PARCopedia* will be tested between June and September 2023, and the first public version of *PARCopedia* is planned to be available online by the end of October 2023. The IT infrastructure of *PARCopedia* will be set up and hosted by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH).

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2. Abbreviations and acronyms¹

API	Application Programming Interface
CARACAL	(Meeting of the) Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP
CL	Chemical Leaders
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) Regulation
CMS	Content Management System
CRA	Chemical Risk Assessment
EB	Editorial Board
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
ET	Editorial Team
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
KMS	Knowledge Management System
ML	Methodology Leader
M18	month 18 since the launch of PARC
NAMs	New Approach Methodologies
NGRA	Next-Generation Risk Assessment

¹ (only recurring abbreviations are listed)

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OECD	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor IDentifier
PARC	European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSbD	Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design
T2.2	PARC Task 2.2 (“knowledge management and uptake into policy”)
US EPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)
WP	Work Package

3. Introduction to *PARCopedia* – context and background

In May 2022, the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC), consisting of national agencies, public health institutes, research institutes, universities and health care organisations from the European Union (EU), Iceland, Israel, Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom, the European Commission and EU agencies as well has set out to innovate chemical risk assessment (CRA) in line with the European Commission’s “Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability”², by identifying research and innovation priorities and developing a corresponding Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA).

PARC has 200 partners³ from 28 countries, including 23 EU Member States, as well as from outside of the EU. It brings together a huge network of European researchers, risk assessors, and policy makers, all engaged in diverse scientific projects and networks of their own, and thereby covers and connects – whether directly or indirectly – a large part of the European as well as a significant fraction of the global CRA community.

Over its seven years of existence, a multitude of projects and activities will be carried out under PARC, many of which overlap in one or more aspects of methodology or scope. It will be one of the most challenging tasks of the Partnership to ensure that the progress in all these

² https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/chemicals-strategy_en, last accessed 2022-12-15

³ In this document, the term “partners” includes both PARC consortium partners and affiliated entities.

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activities is properly tracked and the knowledge generated is made available to all partners as comprehensively as possible and at the earliest convenience. Only in this way will it be possible to avoid unnecessary duplication of work and to exploit PARC's potential for synergies to the maximum.

In some parts of the CRA community, knowledge about/practical experience with the use of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) in CRA is still limited, which forms one of the barriers for the shift from the animal-based testing risk assessment paradigm towards a system of "Next-Generation Risk Assessment" (NGRA).

The use of chemicals – aside from its health and environmental aspects – also has societal, economical and legal dimensions. In this regard, PARC has a high societal responsibility to safeguard that its findings are scientifically sound and robust and, at the same time, adequately communicated to prevent misguided policy decisions. This includes ensuring that the innovation of CRA brought about by the Partnership can successfully support EU policymakers in transforming the European societies towards a more "safe-and-sustainable-by-design" (SSbD) chemicals management.

In PARC, competent authorities from EU Member States and from outside of the EU, other relevant EU regulatory bodies in the field of CRA, but also a significant number of leading research institutions as well as other organisations (via National Hubs) are represented. Bringing all these actors together marks a unique opportunity for accelerating the process of updating CRA regulatory procedures, as PARC offers a forum where all different stakeholders within the CRA landscape can interact and prepare the respective proposals in a more effective and time-saving way. This will help identifying and solving controversial issues at an early stage, thereby potentially facilitating a swifter decision-making process by the relevant official bodies, for example the Meeting of the Competent Authorities for REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals regulation) and Classification and Labelling (CARACAL), the REACH Committee, or the Scientific Committee for Consumer Safety, and finally the European Commission.

With this document, we provide a scoping document for *PARCopedia*, PARC's central platform for knowledge management and dissemination, as well as a space to connect the diverse members of the CRA community and to engage them in broad discussions of the complex issues at hand. The foremost goal of this document is to provide the conceptual basis for the technical implementation and rollout of *PARCopedia*, currently foreseen for month 18 of the Partnership, i.e. by the end of October 2023. However, it also provides the starting point for the continuous further development of *PARCopedia* in later years as a result of the feedback from all involved PARC partners and users.

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4. PARCopedia vision, objectives and scope

Vision

PARCopedia intends to become the **central knowledge base** for CRA in Europe.

PARCopedia intends to become the **central meeting place** for the CRA community in Europe (and an important platform for the CRA community world-wide) for **sharing knowledge and discussing innovation in CRA**.

On these grounds, *PARCopedia* aspires to become a **central community platform for compiling, discussing and disseminating knowledge** on **NAMs**, Next-Generation Risk Assessment (**NGRA**), human and environmental monitoring, and other innovative CRA approaches in - and beyond - Europe. While *PARCopedia* will be a product of PARC, it will not solely focus on PARC results and activities.

In this way, *PARCopedia* aims to **foster both broad and deep understanding** of the inherent potential and limitations of such approaches throughout the CRA community, which will be a **prerequisite for broad acceptance of the transition** towards a new CRA paradigm and, ultimately, **innovative and state-of-the art risk management** of chemicals in Europe.

Main components of *PARCopedia*

PARCopedia is planned to be based on the following three major components:

- a comprehensive knowledge base covering all important aspects of CRA,
- a powerful search engine for CRA-related knowledge on substances, methods, and processes from both inside and outside of PARC,
- a lively community space allowing to create expert profiles, discuss and promote the uptake of innovative CRA approaches and related activities and projects, as well as the knowledge acquired in PARC.

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Specific objectives

PARCopedia strives to:

1. provide easy access to information on all PARC activities (including work packages (WPs), tasks, projects and transversal activities), through links to the PARC website, the PARC internal SharePoint (for PARC users only), and by directly providing summarised information,
2. communicate in a timely way the progress and results from these activities, to allow for optimal integration with other activities and avoid duplication of work,
3. integrate this information with CRA-related knowledge from external sources, for example from other past and present EU and international projects,
4. build a CRA community actively contributing and critically discussing innovative approaches to CRA as well as the priorities under the PARC SRIA,
5. be the point of sharing and communication for the CRA community,
6. allow experts in the various sub-disciplines of CRA to advertise and share their expertise, thereby establishing a network of excellence and
7. enable up-to-date training and capacity building regarding innovative methods for CRA and related topics, by collaborating with the respective PARC WPs and by providing information that facilitates capacity building.

The relationship between *PARCopedia's* specific objectives and PARC's overall strategic objectives is shown in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable..**

Figure 1: Correspondence of *PARCopedia's* specific goals with PARC's overall strategic objectives

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Scope

Target audience

The main target audience of *PARCopedia* is the “Chemical Risk Assessment Community” from both PARC and outside. CRA includes a wide range of scientific, legal and political aspects. As a consequence, this community includes professionals working in the area of CRA in both the scientific and the regulatory field (a non-exhaustive list includes e.g. researchers, risk assessors, risk managers, policy makers, industry, specialised media). It comprises a vast amount of expertise within the scientific domain (human health, environment, ecosystems) as well as beyond, e.g. regarding risk communication and management and policy-making.

The target audience of *PARCopedia* has at least a general understanding of the CRA process, but may have different ideas or points of view due to the different sectors and fields of work and expertise. While experts in their own field, the target audience might not have detailed knowledge about particular aspects outside of their own direct line of work (e.g. policy makers may lack in-depth scientific understanding, while academic researchers may not be familiar with the formal and legal aspects of chemicals regulation). On the other hand, some of the complex issues to be discussed in PARC will require detailed knowledge and scientific expertise.

It will be one of the main challenges of *PARCopedia* to integrate different levels of expertise and needs, and to integrate the diverse CRA community in the discussions while ensuring that complex matters are also adequately addressed.

One of PARC’s main comparative advantages lies in the possibility to interact with different expertise in the CRA community and to exchange, teach and learn about CRA topics that complement the users’ skills and capacities.

Access to *PARCopedia* will be open to all members of the CRA community who fit the above profile.

In contrast, *PARCopedia* is not directed to the general public with little or no scientific training and little or no understanding of the CRA process.

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Knowledge platform

Content featured in *PARCopedia* will include knowledge from inside and outside of PARC⁴ on/relevant for:

- the risk assessment of chemicals or chemical groups (including metabolites and conjugated forms, mixtures etc.) particularly those addressed in PARC. This includes, but is not limited to, knowledge on hazardous properties, potency, presence and prevalence in environmental compartments, toxicokinetics, bioaccumulation and transfer along the food chain, influence of processing, exposure of humans, animals and the environment, risk of detrimental effects, regulatory strategies, risk assessment contexts, regulatory status in EU etc.;
- (non-)test methods (i.e. both experimental and non-experimental methods or approaches that can be used to provide data for the assessment of chemicals) to determine or predict properties of (groups of) chemicals or their concentrations in matrices of interest (e.g. *in vivo*, *in vitro*, *in silico*, analytical methods, ...);
- exposure assessment/estimation methodologies;
- risk assessment methodologies/approaches (e.g. mixture risk assessment approaches, NGRA approaches, SSbD, early warning concepts, ...);
- legislation on chemicals, CRA procedures – including their workflows (incl. the specific risk assessment questions asked), legislation that is relevant to CRA, and regulatory bodies involved;
- risk communication;
- any other technical result produced within PARC.

Community space

PARCopedia will be a community platform for the CRA community that contains "social network"-like profiles, makes expertise visible and accessible (for example that of chemical/methodology leaders), but which will also provide communication tools such as blog spaces, and contains – or embeds - discussion fora and other tools for interaction.

⁴ Content will appear in the form of summaries or other materials provided by WPs, PARC chemical leaders (CLs) and methodology leaders (MLs) as well as individual users.

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Connection with other Work Packages (WPs) in PARC

PARCopedia will be connected to, but will not contain, the information that is already included in other PARC portals provided by the Coordination team (WP 1). Administrative information, internal project documents and project management-related information will be stored in the PARC internal SharePoint, it will be accessed from approved PARC members only. Links to such information will be provided in *PARCopedia*, but only approved users will be able to access it.

PARCopedia will be connected to, but will not normally contain, the content already available on the [PARC website](#). Regular communication with WP3 will appropriately ensure that there will be no duplication of work or competition between the two platforms and that synergies are optimised. The type of content as well as the language used will also vary between the two platforms based on the different objectives and target audiences:

- *PARCopedia* will target the professional CRA community, while the PARC website is directed towards informing all stakeholders of the Partnership about the ongoing activities.
- The PARC website will remain the main channel for disseminating PARC activities and results.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the differences in scope and target audiences of the three different PARC platforms, i.e. PARC internal SharePoint, PARC website and *PARCopedia*.

Figure 2: Differences in scope and target audiences of PARC SharePoint, *PARCopedia* and the PARC website.

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WPs 1 – 9 will all have their own space (“homepage”) in *PARCopedia* for presenting their work to the CRA community in the form of brief descriptions of their work, outputs, progress and interim results. This space will also provide links to other infrastructures or portals containing prediction models (WP 8) or model outputs, measured data and their possible analysis (as managed by WPs 4 and 5 and/or WP 7). *PARCopedia* will e.g. provide the opportunity to link or host knowledge transfer and capacity building initiatives produced by WPs 8 and WP 9 (including the dashboard for laboratory networking). While the technical prerequisites for hosting models or measured data need to be taken into account already in the planning phase, the first version of *PARCopedia* as rolled out by M18 will not yet contain such data.

Other connections could be established at later stages.

PARCopedia will also fulfil the function of a bulletin board, e.g. to inform about upcoming webinars, to present important publications, announce new developments in regulation, etc.

5. Content and knowledge organisation

PARCopedia is expected to be the online content and knowledge management system (CMS, KMS) and community space where users can **search, read, write, share, discuss content**, and **network** on all aspects of CRA.

The use of stringent terminology is important to ensure a common understanding regarding what **content is contained in *PARCopedia***. Therefore, the following operational definitions according to the so-called “DIKW” (Data, Information, Knowledge, Wisdom) model are used:

- **Data** refers to facts, signals, or observations, which, by themselves, have no use or meaning.
- **Information** is data associated with meaning.
- **Knowledge** is information put into context in such a way that it can be used for practical action.

While the borders between these three definitions are fluid to some extent, they are still useful to define the scope of *PARCopedia*’s content (see below).

PARCopedia aims to maximise the **streamlining** and **cross-referencing** of **information** and **knowledge** generated **inside and outside of PARC**.

The **information and knowledge within the *PARCopedia*** CMS can be **captured and presented** through a diverse range of **content types**, including blogs, case studies, reviews, e-books, whitepapers, guides and how-tos, infographics, interactive content, interviews, Q&As,

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listicles, podcasts, social media posts, videos, webinars etc. How this will be done is further discussed later in this document. This diverse range of content types will maximise the digital and online experience of the users.

Aside from formatted text (e.g. html, xml), the *PARCopedia* CMS needs to be capable of accommodating a **range of** word processor, spreadsheet, graphics, presentation (e.g. Microsoft PowerPoint), audio, and video **file formats**. The system should also be able to generate **output files** containing content, whether compiled manually or (semi-)automatically, as PDF, word processor, spreadsheet or graphics files, using templates predefined by the PARC corporate design.

The content of the CMS will be structured based on knowledge organisation principles described further below. Further details in regard to the CMS are described in the section “Elements, functionalities and content presentation” below.

The initial version of PARCopedia will be populated with a first instance of content by T2.2. This content will include publicly available information on topics that are relevant to the scope of PARCopedia, both from within and outside of PARC.

The initial version of PARCopedia will be further populated with content from PARC partners and users. Each PARC WP, task, activity and leader will be asked to share – at minimum - a brief overview of their work, their outputs, and their timelines. They will be able to share and interact with the users on their progress and interim results.

A plan to populate PARCopedia with further content at later stages will be made available in due time before the release of the first PARCopedia version.

As a knowledge platform, *PARCopedia* will heavily rely on the organisation of knowledge. **Knowledge Organisation** is the overall process used within *PARCopedia* to arrange the information and knowledge gathered by PARC and the wider CRA community. Details about the systems and associated methods are described in the section “Knowledge Organisation” below.

Content from within PARC

PARCopedia will provide PARC users with a **tool for presenting and showing** the **progress and results** made within their WPs, Projects, Tasks, and Activities relevant to CRA. Thus, it facilitates and accelerates the **communication** between PARC partners. Furthermore, it will allow PARC members to identify and exploit **information** and **knowledge** regarding substances, methodologies and results generated and/or derived through PARC and beyond.

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PARCopedia will provide a unique meeting point where community members working on the innovation of CRA can share their progress as well as expertise and - in turn - profit from the knowledge and expertise acquired by others.

In this way, *PARCopedia* will be a central instrument for maximising PARC's added value as a true "Partnership" as compared to conventional EU research projects.

"Official" content

One part of the content featured in *PARCopedia* will be generated by users with special author rights and responsibilities, and will be managed and quality-controlled by an Editorial Team situated in T2.2 (see further below, section on roles). This "official" content comprises different parts or sections:

- As its name suggests, *PARCopedia* will feature a wiki-type knowledge base on all matters related to CRA, with a special focus on new and innovative methodology and NGRA. This will help in broadening the knowledge and understanding of such methodologies within the CRA community, thereby – hopefully – aiding in increasing the acceptance for their uptake into regulatory practice. The wiki section will also be designed as a point of reference for assisting community members proficient in different areas of CRA.
- *PARCopedia* will contain a space dedicated to each WP, in particular WPs 4 – 9, for presenting their work to the CRA community, including (links to) their deliverables, reports, publications, special features, webinars for training etc. according to *PARCopedia's* policy and procedures and as FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) Digital Objects.
- *PARCopedia* will contain links to computational models and their output data (WPs 7 and 8) and/or observational and experimental data (as managed by WPs 4 and 5 and/or WP 7). Embedding these connections in the general knowledge structure of *PARCopedia* will also help users find such data more easily.
- *PARCopedia* will also contain links to the dashboard developed by WP 9 containing the data about laboratories, capacities and networks, as well as information on projects, cohorts and monitoring schemes.

The content structure will be created in PARC task 2.2 (T2.2), supported by PARC's chemical leaders (CLs) and methodology leaders (MLs). It will involve "homepages" for relevant substances/methodologies, and summary overviews on selected topics (targeting scientific non-specialists or other specific groups). Further detailed specifications will be established in the first half of PARC year 2, in due time before the release of the first version of *PARCopedia*.

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Personal content

In addition to the “official” content above, *PARCopedia* will also feature personal content, contributed by individual users on their own account and responsibility. In contrast to the “official” content, this content will not be quality-controlled or managed by the Editorial Team. Personal content will, however, have to adhere to the general *PARCopedia* rules and policies, e.g. with respect to copyright, authorship or “netiquette” rules.

Content created by individual *PARCopedia* users includes their personal profiles, with the option of linking out to profiles on other platforms, such as ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier), ResearchGate, LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram etc., and complemented with a blog space to present their research and expertise in more detail, with the goal of enhancing the visibility of the user’s own work. *PARCopedia* will also provide – either directly or by linking out – access to dedicated discussion fora (more details can be found in the following sections).

Contributions from science-to-policy networks (PARC T2.2) and from the synergies network (managed by WP3) will be included as well.

Content from outside of PARC

PARCopedia aims to be a comprehensive platform encompassing, including knowledge on research results, methods and approaches in CRA. It will thus look beyond PARC partners and it will cross-reference or link to content outside of PARC. The links will be established after the first version of *PARCopedia* is rolled out by M18.

For all such connections, it will be the guiding principle not to duplicate work or maintain redundant content. Rather, the goal will be to make best use of third-party content for the purposes of *PARCopedia*, subject to accessibility and possible technical limitations.

High level policies, documents and references

PARCopedia will provide an overview of high-level European and International Policy and Strategy Information that is related to CRA. This includes, but is not limited to, the European Green Deal, the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), the conventions established by the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), such as the Stockholm Convention on persistent organic pollutants (POPs), the Minamata convention on mercury, and the Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management (SAICM), or the Rotterdam convention on pesticides, the Geneva convention on transboundary pollution. It will also include relevant communications from the Directorates-General and EU agencies such as the European

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Chemicals Agency (ECHA), the European Environment Agency (EEA), European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the European Parliament etc., and approaches such as One Health.

There will also be links to documents containing technical information, such as to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)'s Test Guidelines and Guidance Documents, as well as to information on Good Laboratory Practice (GLP), Mutual Acceptance of Data (MAD), reports and reviews. Links to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and other standardisation organisations, or the United Nations' Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS), will also be considered.

Legislation and guidance

Platforms such as [EUR-LEX](#) (i.e. the official website of European Union law and other EU public documents) will be linked to provide information on relevant legislation. Links to supporting guidance on registration requirements for industrial chemicals available on pan-European or other international websites (e.g. those of [ECHA](#), [EFSA](#), the European Commission's Joint Research Centre ([JRC](#)) or the US Environmental Protection Agency ([US EPA](#))) will be provided. Reference to committees and working groups, such as the meeting of the Competent Authorities for REACH and the CLP regulation (CARACAL), or ECHA's Risk Assessment Committee (RAC) could also be made to represent a broad and extensive picture of chemicals regulation.

In addition, links to national competent authorities across regulatory sectors (industrial chemicals, pesticides, cosmetics, food and feed, etc.) will be considered. Links to regulatory action currently under development could be established via links to platforms such as ECHA's Public Activities Coordination Tool ([PACT](#)).

Chemical risk assessment and hazard evaluation frameworks installed by other CRA institutions outside of the EU could also be connected, including the USA, Canada, UK, Japan or Korea (e.g., K-REACH).

Connections to technical references

NAM-specific connections in *PARCopedia* could include tools that support method validation, such as via the Tracking System For Alternative Methods ([TSAR](#)) of the EU Reference Laboratory for alternatives to animal testing ([EURL ECVAM](#)), or the Non-Animal Technologies ([NAT](#)) database. For this purpose, connections with the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development ([OECD](#)), US National Toxicology Program Interagency Center for the Evaluation of Alternative Toxicological Methods ([NICEATM](#)), including the Interagency Coordinating Committee on the Validation of Alternative Methods ([ICCVAM](#)) will be pursued.

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In seeking to strengthen networks, *PARCopedia* could also be connected to national 3R (replacement, refinement and reduction of animals in research) centres and communities such as [RE-Place](#), [Norecopa](#), and the [Animal-Free Research Community](#), as well as to similar projects and collaborations, such as those of the Project Cluster for Implementation of novel Strategies ([ASPIS](#)), the initiative for Accelerating the Pace of Chemical Risk Assessment ([APCRA](#)).

PARCopedia could also include links to past projects and their content (e.g. [EU-ToxRisk or HBM4EU](#)). Furthermore, available EU agencies' guidance on how and when to use NAMs will also be included.

Connections to data platforms/repositories

At the time of writing of this scoping study, the European Agencies have started building a “common data platform” (CDP) for chemical safety in Europe, as initiated by the European Commission in the CSS. It is important to understand that, while the inclusion of certain PARC data portals at a later stage is a possibility, *PARCopedia* is not, at its core, a data repository.

Details regarding the implementation of the CDP are currently not available. It is, however, expected that many fruitful synergies may be established between *PARCopedia* and the CDP, provided the latter will provide functionality for automated access, e.g. by an Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), which would allow *PARCopedia* to retrieve CDP data for its purposes. On the other hand, data generated in PARC (e.g. HBM data) might be better stored on the CDP (but, again, retrievable in addition via *PARCopedia*).

While the actual link between the two platforms will have to be established based on users' needs as well as possible technical constraints, the most important thing at this point in time is to ensure that *PARCopedia* will be technically capable of establishing remote data access. e.g. by including search engines/bots capable not only of searching *PARCopedia* itself.

A connection will be considered with further data platforms such as the OECD [eChemPortal](#) and International Uniform Chemical Information Databases ([IUCLID](#)), the US EPA [CompTox](#) Chemicals Dashboard, the ICE platform by the US NIEHS, the EC's [IPCHEM](#) portal and the [ECHA](#) registration database (both likely to become part of the common data platform in the end), and [i-HBM](#).

Knowledge organisation

This section describes how the sources of information and knowledge summarised in the previous sections can be integrated into *PARCopedia*.

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Knowledge organisation systems include a variety of schemes that organise and manage information and promote knowledge management, such as classification schemes, semantic networks and ontologies.

PARCopedia will reflect the structure of the multiple levels of CRA, from high-level policy to chemical-specific information, and its content should, at all levels, reflect – and, wherever possible, integrate – both environmental and human health. The wide-ranging content will require frequent review to reflect developments, and a fit-for-purpose search engine (see section “Elements”), thereby ensuring that PARCopedia is a valuable, reliable, and up-to-date platform.

Information and knowledge stored in *PARCopedia's* Knowledge Management System (KMS) are associated with certain contexts, e.g. substance (groups), test methods, risk assessment methodologies, legislative framework, etc. These contextual relationships form the basis for users to find, aggregate, sort, filter, or display information and knowledge based on their interaction with the KMS (and CMS).

A non-exhaustive list of contextual associations that can be used to categorise information/knowledge includes:

- type of information, e.g. project report, test method description, etc.,
- related substance,
- related substance group,
- related test or analytical method,
- related toxicological endpoint,
- related risk assessment methodology,
- related chemicals regulation,
- related protection goal (environment, human health, workers, consumers),
- related Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and
- PARC-internal, for registered stakeholders only, open for general public.

On a higher level of abstraction, these associations, which represent aspects of a wider CRA “topology”, can be grouped into different domains.

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Figure 3. A preliminary scheme for the knowledge organisation that will be reflected on PARCopedia. The scheme represented in the figure does not represent the final version.

The scheme above represents a preliminary state of the knowledge organisation that will be subject to further discussions at the later stages, and should therefore not be considered final. In this scheme, any activity or piece of information or knowledge will be associated with one or more of the domains listed below. Domains will be further divided in sub-domains and categories, in alignment with similar activities in PARC, which are not appearing in the representation above at this stage.

- The **chemical domain** pertains to substances, substance groups, mixtures, and articles.
- The **biological domain** encompasses biological systems at different levels of organisation (species/taxa, (sub-) populations, organisms, organ, cellular, or molecular systems), related **biological or biochemical processes** including adverse toxicological effects as organised into “**endpoints**” (at various hierarchy levels), **biological matrices** and **environmental compartments**.
- The **actor domain** denotes institutions (e.g. EU Member State government authorities, public health institutes, global organisations, academic institutions, research institutions) and their roles (e.g. academic researcher, regulatory authority, policy body, e.g. the European Parliament).
- The **approach domain** includes various types of methodologies such as experimental methods and models (e.g. *in vitro* tests acc. to OECD Test Guidelines, chemo-analytical methods for determining a specific chemical in a specific matrix or an *in silico* model for predicting the genotoxicity of chemical substances), but also conceptual approaches such as OECD Defined Approaches or Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATAs).
- The **legislative domain** addresses the legal context and regulatory framework (e.g. REACH or the EU Cosmetics Regulation).

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- The **risk assessment (and also risk management⁵) domain** includes all conceptual aspects of CRA, i.e. the CRA workflows for hazard identification (e.g. classification and labelling) and characterisation (e.g. determination of health-based guidance values), exposure assessment and risk assessment as well as the associated problem formulations and risk assessment questions.
- The **media domain** describes the type (e.g. a report, a podcast etc.) as well as the physical or virtual format (e.g. book, PDF document).

As an example, a risk assessment report based on Human Biomonitoring (HBM) data on bisphenols can be contextually associated with all of the above domains, i.e. with the chemical domain (e.g. bisphenol A and its metabolites, group of bisphenols), the biological domain (species: human, matrix: urine, endpoints: exposure, absorption/distribution/metabolisation/excretion (ADME), the actor domain (e.g. institution: EU Member State authority, role: enforcement of legislation), the approach domain (e.g. analytical methods for measuring bisphenol A in urine, an epidemiological design, but also the methodologies to convert urine levels into external exposure levels or to calculate the overall risk), the legislative domain (e.g. a national enforcement law stipulating the regular monitoring of bisphenol A levels in the population), the risk assessment domain (e.g. specific risk assessment workflow, related risk management options) and the media domain (e.g. it is a report in PDF format).

Semantic annotation or tagging is the process of attaching, to structured or unstructured content, metadata about concepts that are relevant to it. The result of the semantic annotation process is metadata that describes *PARCopedia* content via references to concepts and entities (ontologies). Associations derived from the semantic annotation process can be stored in a hierarchy and/or graph (i.e. CRA topology or “knowledge universe”). Subject to possible technical constraints which need to be further explored, *PARCopedia* will have the option to accommodate harmonised ontologies to maximise the integration of heterogeneities, structured and unstructured content, as well as knowledge graphs to maximise the efficiency of search engines and other algorithms.

The extent to which information/knowledge to be contained in *PARCopedia* needs to be annotated with respect to the above domains (and, if so, what level of detail needs to be

⁵ It is noted that risk management is not in the direct remit of PARC. Nevertheless, all CRA is ultimately linked to risk management and therefore it is foreseeable that knowledge regarding risk management will also be contained in *PARCopedia*.

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represented within each domain) will be subject to further discussion in the weeks and months preceding the rollout of the first *PARCopedia* version (and likely continue afterwards).

Furthermore, as a KMS related to CRA, *PARCopedia* will be equipped with a certain degree of **chemical intelligence**. At the minimum, the system should allow for the association of substance-related information with common chemical identifiers, such as Chemical Abstracts Service Registry Numbers (CASRN), European Community numbers (EC Nos.), or other inventory numbers. However, if this can be realised in terms of possible IT constraints and available resources, it should be capable of handling chemical structure information, for example in the form of SMILES/SMARTS or InChI codes, and have the ability to query the knowledge stored in *PARCopedia* with chemical (sub-)structure searches.

A number of online platforms such as [PubChem](#), [ChemSpider](#), the US EPA's [CompTox](#) dashboard, or the US National Toxicology program's Integrated Chemical Environment ([ICE](#)) provide free inventories of chemical and structural information. It will be subject to further discussion how such inventories could be integrated in *PARCopedia* (and which of them might be best suited for this purpose, also in light of connecting to external databases, e.g. US EPA's ToxCast program, later on).

Accessibility and integration of the sources of information and knowledge outside PARC (summarised in section "Content outside PARC") can be achieved through:

- hyperlinking and cross-referencing,
- implementing APIs and web services, including (semi-)automated routines, and/or
- integrating external search engines to access content that cannot be retrieved or accessed through one of the above.

One of the most important prerequisites for users to find content is a powerful search engine, using state-of-the-art search algorithms, ideally including semantic intelligence, and full-text indexing. Ideally this will also include computational routines for (semi)automated knowledge creation and aggregation. Such routines could perform scans of the knowledge platform, in order to aggregate knowledge on a specific topic on a frequent basis. These search functions and computational routines need an intuitive graphical user interface as well as sorting and filtering functionality. In addition, users should have the possibility to store queries as well as their results for later reference.

Actors and roles

In principle, *PARCopedia* could contain knowledge on different levels of confidentiality. Technically, it would be possible to provide open content for the general CRA community in

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parallel to content restricted to certain users, e.g. active PARC members. On the other hand, such a system would greatly – and perhaps unnecessarily - complicate the day-to-day administration of the system. For this reason, but also since PARC is a partnership fully funded by EU tax payers' money and is devoted to FAIR and open data (and knowledge) sharing, *PARCopedia* will only contain non-confidential information/knowledge that – in principle – could be shared with anybody (notwithstanding appropriate copyright and use right restrictions).

User access to *PARCopedia* will be via an internet browser via the *PARCopedia* URL. A link will also be prominently placed on the PARC main website. The *PARCopedia* URL will also be made findable via the main internet search engines. For access to the content and tools within *PARCopedia*, users will need to register for a user account with their full names. Upon application for registration, users will be asked to demonstrate that they are part of the chemical risk assessment community. While the exact process for user admission is still to be investigated in more detail, the guiding principle should be that the users' identity and affiliation with chemical risk assessment needs to be established as quickly and efficiently as possible. In that regard, possible registration methods discussed (but not finally decided) so far include:

- Users affiliated with a PARC partner or its Affiliated Entity (verification will happen through an institutional email address during the registration process) or belonging to one of PARC's official bodies (PARC Governing Board, Stakeholder Forum, International Board, the list of national institutes provided by PARC's National Hubs Contact Points) will be entitled to join the *PARCopedia* community.
- Users from other institutions with a clear remit in chemical risk assessment could be allowed into PARC if someone who is already registered to *PARCopedia* vouches for them. Once a member from such an institution has been registered to *PARCopedia*, he or she could function as a contact point, confirming the identity of further members from that institution.
- Users not affiliated with such institutions can register to *PARCopedia* if they provide evidence of their involvement in chemical risk assessment, e.g. by providing relevant publications in the field. Other rationales can be considered, e.g. for regulatory risk managers or other experts not covered by the above standard procedures, and applied on a case-by-case basis⁶.

⁶ It is expected that the number of users affected by this more resource-intensive procedure will be fairly low, and therefore manageable.

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All registered users will be able to access the content in *PARCopedia*, add a profile, post blogs and participate to discussion fora.

For user comfort, a single sign-on solution will be developed based on the Open ID standard (an open standard and decentralized authentication protocol that allows users to log in to multiple unrelated websites without having to have a separate identity and password for each). This would also allow for centralised user administration together with further platforms that might be developed under PARC.

Once registered, users, regardless of their role, shall be accompanied by their unique personal profile, which will contain relevant information, such as professional experience and current working status, scientific background and research accomplishments (publications, patents, teaching experience, etc.), links to existing profiles on external platforms, and possible conflicts of interest, in order to guarantee transparency, traceability of the information, and visibility of the users' work. Users will be able to further personalise their profile, e.g. with respect to the content displayed to them. Ideally, they will also be able to set up their personal "dashboard" to freely arrange the content most relevant to them.

PARCopedia users will be categorised by their affiliation and expertise. User management will also allow for profiling users based on the above categories with respect to their specific interests (subject to their consent), to automatically make them aware of new content according to their preferences and expertise.

A non-exhaustive list of affiliation and expertise categories includes:

- system administrators, chemical/methodology leaders, other authors,
- PARC collaborators vs. external users, EU vs. outside of EU,
- domain (research/regulatory/policy/general public) and
- affiliation (industry/academia/government agency/non-governmental organisations (NGO)/policy maker/media/general public).

According to these categories in addition to their interest and expertise, one or multiple roles can be assigned to a user (i.e. Actor - an actor specifies a role played by a user within *PARCopedia*). With respect to user management, each Actor will have different permissions in regard to viewing, editing, or deleting content, including social network-like functions and discussion fora. During the first year the list of main Actors will be revised, and from year 2 onwards it will be tailored to requirements and needs.

The following main Actors with special roles/rights as compared to standard users are identified within *PARCopedia*:

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- **Editorial Board (EB)** – PARCopedia operates under the guidance of the Editorial Board. The Editorial Board is mainly composed of T2.2 members⁷. The board oversees a variety of activities involved in fostering, running, and maintaining PARCopedia. Main responsibilities will include:
 - review, maintain and advise on *PARCopedia*'s policy and governance,
 - increasing visibility and enhancing awareness of *PARCopedia*,
 - promoting *PARCopedia*-related initiatives and activities,
 - attracting new authors/contributors and encouraging submissions,
 - providing expert advice on content and information,
 - enhancing the ability to disseminate current and relevant information,
 - creating a user-friendly and technologically advanced platform to enhance user experience.
- **Authors** - Authors are contributors to *PARCopedia* and should comply with its authorship guidelines and general policy, requiring that authors have made substantial contributions to the content they are willing to share (or, if that is not the case, that the authors of these substantial contributions are made visible), and that they are accountable for the blog post or article, requiring that authors give final approval to the content.

Authors will be held responsible for drafting their blog post or article according to the guidelines for authors developed by the Editorial Board.

PARCopedia authors are asked to share the progress achieved in their work with other community members in a timely fashion, thus enabling timely discussions and the possible uptake of results by other activities within and outside of PARC. It would, however, be up to the individual authors themselves to ensure that such knowledge sharing does not interfere with a later publication of their work, e.g. in a peer-reviewed journal.

CLs and MLs will contribute to *PARCopedia* as authors (both to the “official” and personal content sections, cf. above). Other authors will have the possibility to highlight and feature their content on a voluntary basis, thus increasing their visibility within the community.

- **Knowledge-base and Content Administrators** will support the Editorial Board and content contributors by providing technical support and administrative assistance, including user

⁷ Partners from other PARC WPs may join as well if they move the respective person months (PMs) to Task 2.2 or work on a voluntary basis.

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administration, and copy editing. Furthermore, they will develop and maintain guidelines for Authors regarding the editing style and ensure uniform appearance.

- **IT/System Administrator(s)** is/are responsible for the technical maintenance of the platform PARCopedia in accordance with good administrative practices, including configuration and reliable operation.
- An **Editorial Team (ET)** will be responsible for contributing high-level content, e.g. for providing summarised overviews, but also for covering the population of PARCopedia with relevant content that is not or cannot be provided by the PARC WPs. To this end, the ET will work closely together with PARC CLs and MLs. The ET will also be responsible for Quality Control of the wiki section of the knowledge platform. To this end, a procedure will be developed so that new content to be included in the wiki section will be reviewed by the ET in a timely fashion, acc. to standard operating procedures (SOPs). This will safeguard that information in the wiki is up-to-date and reflects possible differences in opinion within the CRA community or, where that is not yet the case, to make sure that a corresponding disclaimer is included.

In contrast, as noted already elsewhere in this document, content contributed by individual users in their own profile (e.g. as a blog) or as an individual comment on content in the wiki will not be quality-reviewed by the ET.

The ET will be primarily composed of partners from T2.2, however, volunteers from other WPs will be more than welcome to join (no person months from Task 2.2 for this work can however be received).

Moderators will fully understand and enforce the guidelines and policy, and review and monitor participation at *PARCopedia's* discussion fora. Moderators help to maintain a constructive atmosphere and respond or escalate as appropriate when issues or requests are raised. On discussion fora, moderators will generally oversee the discussions with respect to the adherence to the general *PARCopedia* policies, but no capacity exists within T2.2 to fully moderate each discussion within the fora.

For the first version of *PARCopedia*, Administrators and Moderators will consist mainly of Task 2.2 members (but the two roles will be open to volunteers from other WPs, same as the ET). Both roles will be revised as well as possibly extended and altered following the release/rollout of *PARCopedia* by M18, to make sure administrative needs are met. The same will hold for the ET. It is foreseeable that – aside from the daily administration of the system - a significant portion of the person months dedicated to *PARCopedia* by T2.2 partners will be spent on this activity once the conceptual and technical implementation phase will be completed.

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The different Actor roles as well as their interactions are summarised in Figure 4 below. Figure 5 summarises the general workflow for content generation in *PARCopedia*.

Figure 4: Overview of the different Actor roles in administration and moderation of, as well as providing "official" (see text) content for PARCopedia and their mutual interaction. Regarding the inclusion of personal content, cf. Figure 5.

Figure 5: Overview of the general workflow of content (official and personal) generation in PARCopedia

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Legal issues

PARCopedia will only contain non-confidential content.

PARC is funded with EU tax payers' money and therefore access to non-commercial exploitation of the content in *PARCopedia* should be enabled to the greatest extent possible. Creative commons copyrights are therefore being explored for copyright and use rights of the content in *PARCopedia*. In addition, a possible need for disclaimers upon registration for registrants to consent that the content in the website can be used for data analytics (such as use statistics, see sections below) will be investigated.

6. Elements, functionalities and content presentation

PARCopedia presentation

Visual design

The visual design of *PARCopedia* will reflect the visual identity of PARC. *PARCopedia* will visually convey the idea of a wiki, but with a more modern look. The general visual appearance will reflect the design and layout provided by PARC's overall visual design, but possibly with slight deviations, such as a different set of colours, to differentiate the two platforms from each other. Functionality will be prioritised over presentation.

Navigation

Users will start their *PARCopedia* experience from an initial home page containing a short description and a link to the *PARCopedia* registration and login page. After first-time registration, they will be able to enter *PARCopedia* by providing their credentials and clicking on a login button. A start page will appear after login to start navigating *PARCopedia* which will consist of a dashboard that allows for personalised content (cf. "Dashboard"). This will contain the search tool and a main top menu linking to 1) the knowledge base 2) the community space within *PARCopedia* and 3) user manuals and FAQs. A system for storing bookmarks will be available to create shortcuts. A password recovery system will be provided on the login page.

Dashboard

Users will have the possibility to create their personal dashboard, consisting of a page providing quick access to their "favourites", which can be personalised according to the users' interests and needs. The dashboard is planned to be the first page appearing after login. In addition to the main top menu, it will allow the user to include further "widgets", such as e.g.

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a bar of “favourites”, a calendar summarising main events, a newsfeed, the list of all personal notifications, or a box listing trending themes on *PARCopedia*.

Formats

Within entries in the knowledge database, certain different presentation formats can be defined. A non-exhaustive list includes:

- text;
- images;
- videos;
- presentations;
- infographics.

Elements

Knowledge base

The knowledge base of *PARCopedia* will consist of wiki pages for relevant content. Content will be presented in one of the formats mentioned above. Logged-in users will be able to add comments or to react to these entries through reaction buttons similar to social media. Cross-links between wiki pages will allow users to jump from one page to the other.

Search engine

A search engine will provide the opportunity for users to browse content and navigate across different webpages, profiles, discussion fora, and blog spaces. *PARCopedia* search engines will ideally be designed to allow for semantic searches. To the degree achievable with the available resources, the search engine will also possess chemical intelligence that takes into account annotations to the entries, handles information on the chemical structures (such as SMILES/SMART codes or InChI codes), and will integrate the knowledge stored in *PARCopedia* with other PARC platforms, whether ultimately located in- or outside of *PARCopedia* (e.g. PARC website, other WP portals). Subject to possible technical limitations, information from outside of PARC will be included in the results of the searches (e.g. grabbing data via application programming interface, API, or web services).

Different possibilities are under investigation for the best possible tools responding to *PARCopedia*'s needs for the search engine (see “Annex: Technical Specifications”). The engine will ideally allow for elastic searches providing results that are consistent in meaning with the

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search terms, without necessarily integrating the exact search terms, and without the need for manually tagging or annotating the content taken up into *PARCopedia*.

It will be further elaborated whether all of these functionalities can already be provided for the first release of *PARCopedia*. If not, this will however be a priority for the months following its rollout.

Community

Profiles

Personal profile pages will feature content about *PARCopedia* users and summaries of their work. They will contain information on personal expertise and professional backgrounds, and they will provide space for profile pictures, short CVs, contact information, work affiliations, PARC affiliation, subject to what specific users want to share about themselves. From these pages, it will be possible to create further links to their personal profiles in other platforms such as [LinkedIn](#), [ResearchGate](#), and [ORCID](#). Profile pages will provide an opportunity for users to gain visibility. Profiles of major contributors can be highlighted/elevated by system administrators. In contrast to blog functions (described in the next paragraph), the profiles as such will not be used to post updates (like on other social media platforms), but they will serve the purpose of providing basic information on the respective user.

Blogs

A blog space will be available for all users to be able to post blogs related to their work or other PARC-/CRA-related matters by using their personal profiles. Blogs will allow setting links to other *PARCopedia* content.

Discussion fora

To stimulate lively interaction, discussion and knowledge co-creation within the CRA community, meeting places in the form of discussion fora need to be provided by *PARCopedia*. Preferably, such fora would be hosted within *PARCopedia*: among other things, this would allow a more holistic integration into the platform, but also restriction of participation to registered *PARCopedia* users.

At the time of writing this document, different possibilities for such an integrated discussion space are being explored with respect to their technical features and possible functional constraints. As an alternative, in case it turns out that the functionality of the available options lacks important features, the use of external software such as Slack or Discord will be considered. For these, however, an additional login will be necessary for access and their

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management will be to some extent outside of the reach of the *PARCopedia* system administration. Nevertheless, if such an external solution is chosen in the end, links to the existing CRA-related discussions on these platforms will be provided in a central and visible place in *PARCopedia*, to ensure broad participation of the *PARCopedia* community. Also an overview of the topics and focus of discussions of each forum will be provided within *PARCopedia*.

In addition to the above discussion space, message board solutions are currently being explored within T2.2 to allow users to showcase messages and other, more short-lived content (e.g. notice of new publications, upcoming webinars etc.).

7. System administration

General considerations

System administration will include tasks related to user and content management, webpage maintenance and modification and system improvement by regular analysis of use statistics. It will also cover the demands for rebooting the system after a crash. Developers will be responsible for frequent software updates and for creating and maintaining the links to other related platforms.

The *PARCopedia* URL will be <https://www.parcopedia.eu>. The domain will be reserved for 10 years under AUTH's name (the institution under PARC who is in charge for the technical implementation of *PARCopedia*). Before the end of PARC (April 2027), an assessment of the success of *PARCopedia* will be done to decide whether it will be kept after the end of the partnership. In case it is considered useful and successful, the reservation of the domain will be extended. Otherwise, the domain will be kept for the foreseen seven years, providing a three years' time window for closing the website and migrate content, if necessary. Citation on the web will be established once the URL is confirmed. The *PARCopedia* CMS software will be [WordPress](#). WordPress is an open source CMS, which allows to build dynamic websites. It is an easy-to-use and versatile system that can be integrated with additional plugins to accommodate specific needs within *PARCopedia* that are not covered by the WordPress platform itself. Other tools such as Drupal or Django were explored for the main skeleton of the platform, but – in contrast to WordPress - were found not to similarly well address the requirements or the maintenance and management needs of *PARCopedia* in the mid-long term. The feasibility of the tool will be tested, among other things, during a beta test.

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Performance-wise, the system will initially be set up to allow 1 000 users to use and work on *PARCopedia* at the same time.

Costs of *PARCopedia* will be covered through the funds of PARC.

User management and user support

Users will register to *PARCopedia* by filling a registration form containing details of their full real names, email addresses and affiliations. While registration will be open to everyone, it will need approval by the system administrator(s) based on the completeness of the information provided and the compliance with the requirements. Users will then receive automatic notifications of registration approval.

Within *PARCopedia* – and also in the associated discussion fora – users have to use their real names and their name will be visible with every contribution they make).

Users will be held responsible for the content they will provide in their profiles, in their blogs and in discussion fora. *PARCopedia* authors will also be requested to keep the content they provided up-to-date. The editorial team will be responsible for the actuality of the content within the *PARCopedia* wiki pages.

Existing conflict of interest will need be declared upon registration. A sample declaration is provided below:

“I hereby declare that the disclosed information is correct. I undertake to inform you of any change in these circumstances, including if an issue arises during the course of the meeting or work itself.”

Users will be required to display a responsible and appropriate conduct in discussion fora and when using any interactive tool in *PARCopedia*. The exchange of opinions and ideas will be promoted as long as the general rules and code of conduct of *PARCopedia* will be followed.

Different types of rights will exist in *PARCopedia* ranging from read-only, to read-and-edit, to system administration and will be assigned based on the roles within PARC. System administrators will have the opportunity to elevate the rights of selected users and to highlight their profiles.

A Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) page will exist, providing access to the *PARCopedia* help desk and featuring a *PARCopedia* user’s manual. These will be in written format, which might be complemented with video-tutorials. These features will provide users with the support they need to independently access all the features of *PARCopedia*.

Only System Administrators will have access to the administrative area of the website (backend), where content visible in the frontend can be created and managed.

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Legal considerations

PARCopedia will comply with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). *PARCopedia* users will agree on complying with the EU GDPR and other relevant laws at the registration stage.

Disclaimer text will be added to *PARCopedia* to avoid any legal liabilities, and delegate content responsibility to the authors.

Rules and Code of Conduct

A set of rules will be created to manage the registration process and to establish who will be able to register to *PARCopedia* and under which requirements. They will ensure that legitimate intellectual property rights are respected, that work will not be plagiarised and relevant credits to the originators of idea are given.

A code of conduct for *PARCopedia* general usage will be made available, and by registering to *PARCopedia*, users will consent to it. This will include community rules, such as the discussion group etiquette.

Uploading defamatory, abusive, threatening, offensive, or illegal material will be strictly prohibited.

Discriminatory, hostile or intimidating messages or language will not be tolerated, whether based on a person's race, ethnicity, culture, national origin, social or economic class, educational level, sex, sexual orientation, gender identity and expression, age, size, family status, political belief, religion, or mental or physical ability.

The consequences of breaching the code of conduct will be made clear as part of that code. The EB will be in charge of managing possible code breaches. Affected users will have the right to appeal the corresponding EB decisions (see next section).

Ombudsperson

For cases of potential conflict such as inappropriate content or maladministration, *PARCopedia* will have an Ombudsperson. This person (or group of designated persons) will provide resources for handling complaints and informal conflict resolutions that may arise. This/these person(s) will aim at facilitating communications and at offering mediation.

The Ombudsperson(s) will remain independent and neutral. The person(s) will exercise good judgment. The identity of those seeking these services will remain undisclosed if desired. A link between the Ombudsperson(s) and PARC management board will be established.

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Use statistics

Use statistics will be analysed on a regular basis for the purpose of identifying areas of the system that are highly or rarely frequented and to make necessary improvements. Use statistics will also provide a means of evaluation of the acceptance and uptake of the system by the community.

All quantitative and quality indicators, parameters, goals will be aligned with the *PARCopedia* specific objectives and their definition will depend on the functionalities offered by the technology stack used for *PARCopedia* development, as well as on the total number of *PARCopedia* users and the development stage of the platform. Indicators will include:

1. the number of accesses to the different pages, including the level of engagement on the content provided and
2. the usage of interactive tools and various features in *PARCopedia* by the users.

8. Stepwise plan for technical implementation

Pre-rollout phase: *PARCopedia* pilot

Organisation and coordination:

Through this scoping document, the content, purpose and the target audience of *PARCopedia* are defined, and the minimum requirements and the overall aspect of *PARCopedia* are established. Several technical options for the development and implementation of *PARCopedia* exist that were presented earlier in this document. While the main tool to develop *PARCopedia* is set to be WordPress, the different possible plugins will be tested by T2.2 to determine the best possible solution for *PARCopedia*.

Until M18 (the foreseen launch of *PARCopedia*), T2.2 will create a skeleton website, to which a first set of wiki pages and examples for both the knowledge base and the community space (including profiles and blogs) are added and then successively extended. The initial content for the wiki pages will be taken inter alia from already existing, freely available content (e.g. actual wiki pages can be embedded into *PARCopedia* or some content that can be duplicated from [HBM4EU](#)).

In parallel to the compilation of an initial set of relevant content, the actual frontend and backend development will occur, and a (non-public) beta version of *PARCopedia* will be launched. This version will be used as a test, and the feedback obtained by various users from

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within PARC at this stage will be used to improve *PARCopedia* as well as to collect FAQs and necessary manuals for users and system administrators. The beta version will include a space for users to report any possible bug in the system.

Minimum features

The beta version of *PARCopedia* will include the following minimum features:

- knowledge storage and presentation: structure, look and feel, limited number of examples;
- information search/aggregation tool: basic functionalities;
- community platform: test accounts created for different roles, exemplary accounts;
- discussion fora: at least one example;
- administrative features: user management and, if possible, statistics.

Rollout by M18

Organisation and coordination

The beta version of *PARCopedia* will be tested from June to September 2023. All the technical improvements, software and hardware updates, extra content and extra features, and users' feedback will be implemented afterwards and the first public version of *PARCopedia* will be launched at the end of October 2023.

A communication campaign for the launch of *PARCopedia* is foreseen. Modalities (e.g. the staging of a formal launch event) and phases of this launch will be further investigated within T2.2. with the support of WP 3. *PARCopedia* will be advertised in and outside of PARC, inter alia at an ECHA workshop on NAMs on 1 June, and during the WC 12 (12th World Congress on Alternative Methods to Animal Testing, at the end of August 2023) and EUROTOX (congress of the European Societies of Toxicology, in mid-September 2023) conferences.

Minimum features

At the launch of *PARCopedia*, the visual identity will be implemented. All features such as user registration, profile generation, knowledge base, and community space will be ready and fully functional. The initial content will feature at least an overview of the different WPs and their tasks, projects and activities.

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Next phases

After *PARCopedia* has become fully operational, it will be maintained, and use statistics will be regularly checked to optimise the platform and the user experience, and to ensure its objectives are achieved.

The focus in later years will be on adding functionality which could not be implemented in the first version, on providing additional content, on connecting *PARCopedia* to external data sources and platforms and on the sustainability of the existence and use of *PARCopedia* after the seven years of PARC.

Figure 6 summarises the technical implementation phases of the *PARCopedia* platform along with a tentative timeline for their implementation.

Figure 6: Stages of the *PARCopedia* technical implementation plan.

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9. Annex: technical specifications

Description of the hardware

PARCopedia will be hosted by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) IT Centre. AUTH's IT centre has provided the Environmental Engineering Laboratory (EnveLab) with two virtual machines (computer resources that use software instead of a physical computer to run programs and deploy applications) that are readily available for the development of the platform. One of these machines will be used as a development server and the other one as a production server. *PARCopedia* will be initially developed and tested in the first server and will be launched officially on the second server respectively. Virtual Machines will protect the project development cycle from hardware problems, connectivity and cabling issues. Their hosting infrastructure offers high availability, service guarantee and protection from malfunctions and power outages.

The IT AUTH centre's infrastructure operates in different physical spaces (data centres) which allows for disaster aversion and recovery, even in the event of a physical disaster. The centre's infrastructure is also constantly kept up-to-date with the latest hardware and software which allows virtual machines to operate with faster speed and new features. This will allow *PARCopedia* to keep up with the highest standards for many years, even after the project's end.

The Virtual Machines will sport two 2.8 GHz processors and 8 GB of RAM. After *PARCopedia* goes into production and should the need for additional resources arise, the virtual machines will be upgraded accordingly.

EnveLab has reserved a total space of 20 TB for *PARCopedia*.

Initial space allocation for *PARCopedia* is set to 5 GB of data storage, which will be increased depending on the platform's needs. The AUTH IT Centre is responsible for allocating said extra space.

Performance-wise, the system will be planned to allow 1 000 users to work on *PARCopedia* at the same time, which should allow enough capacity to avoid a system crash.

Description of the software

Initial development will be based on the WordPress CMS along with the use of certain plugins to cover basic functionality. The proposed plugins considered so far include BuddyPress, which provides a social network platform along with BuddyPress Docs which provides a part wiki, part document editor, part shared Dropbox work space that will be used to create wiki pages. This will not be a tool for the community of *PARCopedia* users, but it will provide the possibility

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to authors and editors to collaborate on the content of wiki pages. Other plugins currently considered include [Youzify](#) (for the community part of PARCopedia), [BetterDocs](#) (for the wiki part), and [ACF](#) (for the message-board part).

In addition, a number of search engine plugins will be tested in order to investigate its functionality. Options under investigation so far are:

- SearchWP,
- Relevanssi,
- Swiftype,
- Ajax,
- Ivory and
- AI Engine.

If none of the options mentioned above provides an adequate solution, then the possibility to develop a custom search engine from scratch will be investigated, however, it is not clear at this point whether such a solution can be provided.

For the community space to allow users to have easy-to-find messages, a modern style message board can be used within the *PARCopedia* platform. An integrated solution would be preferred (cf. above), but this could be complemented by linking to external media platforms, for which the preferred software options would be Slack or Discord.

- Slack is a messaging app for business that connects people to the information they need.
- Discord is a Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP, a technology that allows for vocal calls using internet connection) and instant messaging social media platform. Users have the ability to communicate with voice calls, video calls, text messaging, media and files in private chats or as part of communities called “servers”.

Maintenance plan

PARCopedia will mainly be maintained by the AUTH IT team in charge of *PARCopedia* for the duration of the project. Administration privileges and access to the backend will be granted to selected individuals in order to ensure continuous support and quick moderation.

After the platform is set up and running, the EnveLab IT team will be responsible for keeping the platform up-to-date, along with the rest of the administrators/moderators.

